

Wireless Montenegro: A Free Internet Service for Citizens or Just a Government Project toward the European Union Accession Process?

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Abstract

As part of Montenegro's path towards accession to the European Union, the progress of the state administration is reflected through the negotiation process in 33 chapters. One of the most important chapters is on Information Society and Media, which among other things seeks to raise transparency, political participation and social inclusion. The authorities are working on the improvement and promotion of the information society in Montenegro, and are trying to enable citizens to use ICT in order to achieve certain rights similar to those of developed European countries. The recently launched project, Wireless Montenegro, aims to enable all citizens free wireless Internet and thereby access to various electronic services that have been imposed as part of the negotiation process. Is "Wireless Montenegro" just another project that needs to simulate the real commitment of the government to promote a democratic environment and reduce social exclusion, or is it an honest and well-envisaged project? To illustrate the situation in the Montenegrin towns, we used quantitative analysis. We have compared the situation with neighbouring Croatia which is now an EU member state, concerning the number of connections to free wireless networks, the number of access points and the dynamics of development, as well as plans for the expansion of the project. Together with the results of a survey of Montenegrin citizens and a qualitative analysis of the socio-economic environment and the complex political reality, it was concluded that Wireless Montenegro represents yet another project which failed in its function. Explaining the potential reasons why the state administration is not more committed to fostering an ICT environment, recommendations were offered to accelerate the achievement of European objectives and the development of e-democracy.

Keywords: Wireless Montenegro, negotiations, European Union, e-democracy, participation.

Introduction

Montenegro became a candidate country for membership of the European Union (EU) in December 2010. In mid-2012, negotiations began with the EU bodies with the aim Montenegro reaching the level of development, standards and practices of other EU member states at the moment of accession to this community. Negotiations are organized through 33 different chapters, but the main focus is on the rule of law, and fighting against organized crime and corruption. In this regard, in order to increase transparency, one of the most important chapters that was opened at a conference in Brussels in March 2014 is "Information society and media". Engaging citizens through digital media includes enhancing active participation in law-making, policy-making and legislative processes (Caldow, 2004). Although it was noticed that Montenegro has reached a good level of compliance with the EU acquis in the field of electronic communications, information society, and audio-visual policy, it still does not recognize sufficient transparency of state bodies and local governments (Radunović, 2015b), nor the involvement of citizens in decision-making. Throughout the *Comparative Project on Local e-democracy Initiatives in Europe and North America* (Peart & Diaz, 2007), we need e-democracy initiatives for a democratic process which should enhance transparency, participation and deliberation. However, the situation in Montenegro is now much better than in previous years, and a series of legislative acts that regulate the field of e-governance, the use of electronic documents, and electronic signatures, has already been adopted. The national team for incident management on the Internet (CIRT) has been formed, alongside the establishment of portal www.euprava.me, which offers electronic services to citizens and companies within the jurisdiction of public administration. At the same time, the Laws on Electronic Communications, Postal Services, Electronic Administration and other areas, were passed on the basis of the guidelines of European officials. However, Montenegro shows, as in other areas, that the main problem is not non-existent or poor legislation, but the non-implementation of legal provisions in practice. That is why the EU insists that the government finally has to demonstrate that the laws are respected, and that any breach of the law must carry the proper punishment. However, to date there are still no final verdicts on political assassinations, corruption and organized crime. The media is dealing with these problems on a daily basis, and they have also become a target, because we have frequent attacks on journalists and their property (Dan on-line, 2015). In order to enable citizens to participate in decision-making, to communicate with

administration and to achieve their rights more easily, it seems that the Montenegrin authorities are constantly working on improving the environment when Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) come into question. The question is whether or not there really is a genuine effort to provide the kind of services for citizens that are already available in developed democracies (Peart & Diaz, 2007), or, as in some other areas, it is just a performance for the officials of the European Union, and material which just formally serves to improve the tone of reports in the accession process? In the *Handbook on e-democracy*, Reinsalu (2010) points out that e-participation is a necessary component or even, more precisely, a prerequisite of democracy. One of the biggest steps forward so far for the development of the Information Society in Montenegro, which aims to offer free Internet to all citizens, and to create preconditions for easier communication with the public administration, is the project "Wireless Montenegro", which the citizens of Montenegro have perceived in different ways. How this project has been developed; what is comparative practice is like in Croatia; and, how this service is used and perceived by Montenegrin citizens, form some of the questions examined in this paper.

Free Internet for Citizens - the Intention or the Pressure of the EU?

Immediately after 2010 when Montenegro became a candidate country for membership of the EU, the Montenegrin government became aware of the obligations that had to do more with satisfying the public interest. One of the identified activities in this regard was an attempt to provide efficient communication services for the security and emergency services in Montenegro. To develop such a service, the Government made a public-private partnership with an Austrian investor EOSS Industries Holding, and formed a company "Wireless Montenegro". That new radio network developed for the security services and government bodies, started to operate in November 2012. In early 2013, after negotiations with the EU had started, the government changed its decision, and announced its intention to provide a free Internet service for all citizens through project "Wireless Montenegro" (Hadžalić, 2013). Although initially the project had been developed only for certain state institutions (Kalač, 2011).

An exquisitely formed action, especially for the socially vulnerable and those who can't afford the luxury of the Internet in the 21st century, was then announced by the Ministry for Information Society and

Telecommunications (MIDT). But how much has been carried out so far? The project was implemented only in 8 cities: Podgorica, Budva, Nikšić, Bar, Kotor, Bijelo Polje, Tivat and Pljevlja. In the official report of the Ministry for 2014, it was written that: “Wireless Internet connection is provided at 40 locations in 10 cities in Montenegro” (MIDT, 2015a), while on the official website of the MIDT, we have information that it is provided in only 8 cities - missing off Žabljak and Berane (MIDT, 2015b). At the same time, on the official website of the company. “Wireless Montenegro” which is implementing the project together with the Government, we have information that the signal covers 9 cities (Wireless Montenegro, 2015), where the centre of Berane is added to the above list, but there is no Žabljak municipality! Which of the following pieces of information is correct - 8, 9 or 10 cities? The largest number of access points (AP) is set in the capital city of Podgorica -with a total of 14 locations, while in the municipality of Tivat, signal covers only one location – the Airport. According to the available data, very small areas are covered by an Internet signal in Pljevlja, Bijelo Polje and Kotor.

However, it should be noted that some of the local government areas, which are not envisaged by the “Wireless Montenegro” project, have already been independently provided with free wireless Internet in some parts of their cities. Such services exist in Cetinje, Budva, Tivat, Berane, Pljevlja, Bijelo Polje and Podgorica, but it is still a different network with different characteristics and qualities of service.

The dynamics of the development and dissemination of the “Wireless Montenegro” project obviously have not been carried out satisfactory throughout Montenegro. This is obvious if one takes into account that since the project was first launched and up until February 2014, it was not possible to connect up to the network “Free Montenegro” except in Podgorica and Budva. By the end of 2014, the network had spread to 6 (or 7) other cities with insufficient access points, and this would appear to be so without any proper advertisement. Throughout this project, people can use only some of the basic and undemanding services, and if we know that there is not a large number of locations where the service can be used, the question arises to whom is the service being aimed at? The point becomes clearer when one looks at MIDT's Report for 2014 where it is clearly stated that the priorities and all activities are mainly carried out in order to meet the negotiating processes with the EU. Thus, it is explicitly stated that:

“The portal of electronic government, which represents the electronic counter for access administration at the state and local level, at the end of 2014

offers a total of 77 on-line services. In this context, as the most important activities of the Ministry in the past year, we emphasize the following:

- The opening of negotiations for the chapter 10 “Information society and media”;
- The implementation of obligations on the agenda of the Government as a percentage of 92.9% ... (MIDT, 2015a: 4)

This clearly indicates that the priority is on meeting the expectations of European Commission officials. Of course, this does not mean that there is no will to provide well-being for citizens, but it is obvious that it represents only a consequence, and not a cause of action.

In a country where a large number of citizens do not have any decent economic and social status, it seems that for many of them this project makes little sense and is not really of any significance. This is because a prerequisite to use this service is to have the time and inclination to look for locations where the service is actually available, then to go there, and to be in possession of some of the portable devices that can gain access to the wireless Internet! According to Mahrer and Krimmer (2005) e-democracy is not just about technology but also impacts on every aspect of any organization that is involved in the process. Paradoxically, this project will obviously have a very small effect on socially disadvantaged and marginalized groups, that is, for those who might be in the most need of such service.

So Close and yet So Far

In order to strengthen its capacity and to develop the necessary ICT services and infrastructure for raising transparency, and to be able to effectively deliver some services to their citizens, through the process of accession, the EU has enabled Montenegro to use pre-accession funds as well as the knowledge and practice of the developed EU countries (MIDT, 2013). The Montenegrin authorities were given the opportunity to collaborate, among others, with colleagues from Estonia, at the elections held in March 2015 when more than 176,000 people had voted electronically! Also, they have been cooperating with the Italians, whose government introduced a free WiFi with more than 3,000 AP across the country (Free Italia WiFi, 2014). However, when it comes to WiFi Internet, the United Kingdom is in front of others on this issue with over 5 million installed AP. Finland has declared the Internet to be a human right, and has set the minimum speed of Internet access, and so has Spain. Croatia joined them on

I January 2015, and its “Universal Service Operator” must ensure that a minimum access speed to the Internet is at least 1 Mbps, for all users.

Since July 2013, neighbouring Croatia, has been a member of the EU. Anyone who follows developments in the Western Balkans, knows that Croatia together with Slovenia, is one of the countries of the former Yugoslavia, which has gone further than others when it comes to carrying out the practice and enforcing the standards of the developed democracies of Europe. In addition to guaranteed rights, Croatia has been working intensively on the development of a free Internet service for its citizens and visiting tourists. In that regard numerous electronic services have been developed in order to enable citizens to accomplish their rights quickly and efficiently, especially in terms of communication with local and state administrations.

Thus, for example, the city of Rijeka launched the free WiFi Internet for its citizens in June 2007. The signal was then released in a few locations in the city centre, but with 27 AP installed. The number of AP at the beginning of 2008 increased to 39, while the flow rate increased from 5 Mbps to 10 Mbps. During that period the number of daily connections increased from an initial 173/day on average, to 480/day, and the signal strength was around 50db (Petрак, 2009). Taking into account the signal strength with respect to the size of the coverage area, this WiFi zone seemed to be of the highest quality in Croatia (Lokal Patrioti Rijeka-Fiume, 2012). After the first year of using this service, the number of average connections was 748/day, and after two years that number rose to approximately 1,500 connections per day (Grad Rijeka, 2014). The city was further developing the service and covered almost all frequent locations, so that the total number of AP increased to 95, with the maximum number of 5,400 users who can simultaneously use free WiFi. At the same time, the flow of the wireless Internet access increased to 50 Mbps.

Following the practice of the city of Rijeka, Croatia soon realized the advantages of the free WiFi in every sense, and decided to introduce an expansion of that system. Through the project "Hotspot Croatia", in mid-2014, the Ministry of Tourism has installed 270 AP in various cities, and announced that by the end of that year the number of AP will exceed 500 (Kako na web, 2014).

Research Methodology

This study was conducted on a sample of 400 respondents. I have interviewed citizens in Podgorica, Budva and Nikšić as the cities with the largest

number of installed access points. Those cities represent all three regions in Montenegro, with a total population of 623,000 people according to 2011 census. In the capital city of Podgorica with 180,000 people, where the highest number of sites is covered by the free WiFi signal, the sample was 250 people. In Nikšić, municipality with about 56,000 citizens in the city itself, the sample was 100 people. In Budva with around 19,000 inhabitants, 50 people were interviewed. The survey was conducted in 2014 as follows: in Podgorica on November 23 and 24, in Nikšić on November 28, in Budva on November 30. There was a total of 237 men (59.25% of the total sample) and 163 women (40.75%), aged 15-70 years. The sample included 96 citizens of age 15-25 years (24%), 192 of age 25-45 years (48%), 76 of age 45-60 years (19%) and 36 of age 60-70 years (9%), (Figure 1). Among them, there were 140 high school or faculty students (35%), 212 employed persons (53%) and 48 unemployed (12%) including 20 pensioners (5%). In the total sample, 212 respondents have completed high school (53%), 144 have completed university education (36%), while 44 have completed primary school or are currently attending high school (11%). Respondents answered the following questions:

1. Do you have a smart phone, laptop or tablet you can use to access the Internet? (Offered answers: Yes, No);

2. Are you familiar with the project "Wireless Montenegro" and have you used the free web "Free Montenegro"? (Offered answers: I am familiar with it and I have used the service, I am familiar with it but I haven't used the service, I am not familiar with it but I have used the service (this particular answer was offered since there were a number of people who have been using this free wi-fi service, but they hadn't heard anything about the project "Wireless Montenegro"), I am not familiar with it and I have never used the service);

3. How many times have you used the free WiFi signal "Free Montenegro" and are you satisfied with the quality of service (acquired speed connections, flow and method of use of the service)? (Offered answers: I used it up to 10 times, I used it up to 50 times, I used it over 50 times; I am satisfied with the quality of service, I am not satisfied with the quality of service);

4. Have you used network "Free Montenegro" for communication with some state or local authority, and how many times? (Offered answers: Yes, I have - once, up to 10 times, more than 10 times; No, I have not);

5. Do you know on which sites free WiFi "Free Montenegro" can be used and are you willing to go to those locations only for using free Internet? (Offered answers: I know some sites, I don't know any of the sites; I would go to the site to use free Internet, I wouldn't go to the site to use free Internet);

6. Do you feel that the state is doing enough to facilitate access to free wireless Internet? (Offered answers: Yes, No, I am not sure);

7. Do you believe that the free WiFi provide by the government is connected with the process of accession to the European Union and, if so, in what way? (Offered answers: I believe that is associated with the accession to the EU—The state wants to please its citizens, the state wants to please the representatives of the EU, something else ...; I believe that is not related to the EU accession process; I am not sure);

8. Do you recommend your friends to use this service? (Offered answers: Yes, No, Occasionally);

Interviews were conducted on the streets, in direct communication with respondents, and with 200 of them, at locations where it the free wireless signal “Free Montenegro” was available, and with the rest of the 200 respondents at locations where there was no signal nor any AP. Part of the respondents who answered that they didn’t use the network “Free Montenegro”, were not responding to questions about the quality of the network and about the usage of the service for communications with some administrative authority (questions 3 and 4).

The results that were obtained were analysed together with the collected data on the number of sites and the number of access points in the cities, along with official documents from the Government of Montenegro in the context of accession negotiations. Also, I have used a comparative analysis with data gathered from Croatia.

Research Results

The largest number of APs and locations where it is possible to use the free wireless Internet “Free Montenegro”, are located in Podgorica and Budva, where the project had been initiated. In Nikšić, the service became available at the end of February 2014. It is interesting to note that just ten days after Nikšić gained this service, the Ministry for Information Society and Telecommunications announced that the number of previously generated connections crossed the 1.1 million mark (Kodex, 2014). Only two months previously, at the end of 2013, the same Ministry stated that the number of connections was 300,000 (MINA business, 2014) with an almost identical number of available APs. It is interesting that, according to the data made available at that time, the largest number of connections, almost one fifth of the

total, was realized within the Clinical Center in Podgorica, and then followed by the faculty buildings and airports (MIDT, 2014). The yearly report of MIDT for 2014, states that the actual number of connections by the end of 2014 was 14,000,000. It is unclear why the same report, only a few pages further on, noted that 27,268,239 connections had been accomplished. (MIDT, 2015a: 19). But if we consider for instance, that in the city of Rijeka in Croatia, with 128,000 inhabitants, a total of 2,000 connections were achieved per day on an average basis, which is annually around 700,000 connections, it turns out that the percentage of Montenegrins who use free Internet is much more than that of the Croats. This data can be interpreted from different perspectives. First, we should bear in mind that mobile operators in Croatia from an earlier time have offered the Internet at very affordable prices with corresponding packages. Then, a large number of cafes and restaurants also offer a free Internet service in order to attract visitors. Additionally, the fact that Montenegrins are still at the top of the statistics in Europe when it comes to the use of mobile phones with 178 subscribers per 100 inhabitants, while Croats have 113 mobile subscribers per 100 inhabitants, it becomes clearer that perhaps the need of Montenegrins to possess mobile phones affects a large number of connections (Bljesak, 2013). In addition, the financial situation in Montenegro is far worse than in Croatia, with the monthly average salary in Croatia amounted to being around € 730 in mid-2014, while in Montenegro was €473 (Vijesti online, 2014).

However, it is important for us to see the perception of citizens regarding the Government's intention of developing the project "Wireless Montenegro": Was it meant for citizens and to increase efficiency and transparency, or was its purpose just to please the EU officials? Out of the total of 400 citizens surveyed, 63 of them (15.7%) responded that they did not have a laptop, tablet or smart phone for WiFi access. Among the remaining 337 respondents, 212 (53%) responded that they were familiar with the project "Wireless Montenegro" and that they had been using that service (Figure 2). Although, the number of those who had never heard of the service was 105 (26.5%), assuming that neither of those 63 people, who don't have a device for WiFi, have not heard of the service, the number of the uninformed would increase to 168, which represents 42% of the total sample. However, we have as well to factor in those who have declared that they are not familiar with the project, but that they have used the network "Free Montenegro" - their number is 13 (3.25% of the sample), and 7 respondents stated that they are familiar with it, but they have not used that service (1.75%).

Out of the 225 respondents who have used the service (Figure 3a), 113 were from Podgorica, 75 from Nikšić and 37 from Budva.

When asked how many times they used the service and whether or not they were satisfied with its quality, 47 respondents claimed to have used the service up to 10 times (11.75% of the total sample), the service was used up to 50 times by 118 respondents (29.5%), while the remaining 60 users accomplished connections more than 50 times (15%) (Figure 4). Interestingly, out of 225 who have used the service, 192 users were satisfied with the quality of the service, which is about 85% of all users (or 48% of the total sample), while the number of those who were dissatisfied was 33, which is almost 15% of users (8.25% of the total sample) (Figure 3b).

A very interesting fact for us is that only 13 respondents answered that they have used the network "Free Montenegro" to communicate with any state or local government authorities (3.25% of the total sample), and in each case they did it only once (Figure 5).

More than half of the respondents, 212, answered that they know where some sites with free Internet are (53%), but only 27 of them would be willing to go to some location in case they needed the Internet (6.75%).

It is interesting that only 42 respondents felt that the Government was doing enough to provide free Internet for the citizens of Montenegro (10.5%), while 149 of them were not sure (37.25%). The remaining 209 are not satisfied with the government's efforts in this field (52.25%) (Figure 6). Among the 42 who were satisfied, 34 respondents were not employed or were retired, which seems very strange, especially if one considers that among them, there are 25 participants who have not tried this service at all (Figure 7). Apparently, most of those who have been using the service and are familiar with the project "Wireless Montenegro", think the Government could do much more than at present- only 17 respondents which are service users, were satisfied with the efforts and activities of the state about the free WiFi (4.25% of the total sample)!

Out of 400, 288 respondents (72%) consider that the free Internet service totally caught up in the process of accession to the EU, while 100 respondents (25%) do not perceive this. Only 12 of the respondents (3%) were not sure (Figure 8). It is interesting that among those 288 who see a connection with the accession process, 144 respondents were those who have a higher or university education. Also, 173 respondents believe that the primary objective of this project is to satisfy EU officials (43.25%), while 112 respondents considered that service is because of the needs of the citizens (28%). The rest of the respondents, 115 (28.75%), had different attitudes (Figure 9).

A total of 325 respondents (81.25%) recommend this service to their friends and acquaintances, which is interesting if we know that some of them were not familiar with the project “Wireless Montenegro”, or had not even got a device for accessing WiFi. Obviously, anyone who is familiar with the project also recommends this service, while it is understandable that some of the respondents who did not know about the project, could not recommend it (18.75% of the sample).

Conclusions

Research in Podgorica, Budva and Nikšić, was conducted on a sample of 400 respondents. The results show that over 81% of respondents support the government's efforts to develop the service, and they recommend this service to others. However, only 4.25% of total respondents who have used the service consider that the government is doing enough to develop this service, which indicates some dissatisfaction with the current state of affairs. The results show that only about 56% of the respondents have used the service and that among them are some users who didn't know anything about the project. That fact alone supports the thesis that the government simply has not done enough regarding the promotion of the project. On the official website of the city of Bar, it is written that this project was initiated because the requirement is being put in front of Montenegro on its path to EU and NATO accession (Opština Bar, 2014). On the MIDT's website there is a section dedicated to this project, but other than a few appearances in the media, officials of the Ministry have simply not promoted this project significantly enough. On the quality of this service, 85% of those who used it are satisfied. While the idea of the Montenegrin authorities with regard to this project is to allow free WiFi to all citizens, neighbouring Croatia has recognized the potential of free WiFi for developing its tourism. Croats placed around 500 APs for free Internet, whilst the Montenegrins placed only 40. If we compare Podgorica with its 186,000 inhabitants and only 15 APs, with Rijeka in Croatia where 123,000 people live and where 95 APs have been set up (Figure 10), it becomes clear that the Montenegrin authorities have a lot more to do, in order to reach the level of the standards of their EU neighbours. However, in each of the plans, strategies and reports, the relevant Ministry stated that this project was designed with the aim of involving citizens in the information society, and for the improvement of electronic communication between citizens and administrations. Regardless of this, the results of this survey have demonstrated that only about 3% of

respondents have actually used the network “Free Montenegro” to communicate with the state or local government. Each of them did it only once, so it is clear that this service will not be used for intensive communication between citizens and the administrations in the near future. Whether the reason for this is the lack of adequate electronic services offered by the government or something else, a possible cause could be sought in the perception of citizens about what the goal of the Montenegrin government with “Wireless Montenegro” actually was. Citizens obviously do not believe that the government’s intention regarding the project, was aimed at the benefit of the citizens, as over 70% of them declared that the project “Wireless Montenegro” only exists because of the EU accession process. We have the same percentage of those who believe that this project aims to satisfy the EU officials or some personal interests of certain politicians. Only 28% of respondents believe that the service is meant for the general population, which implies that citizens in general believe that the government is working under pressure from the EU. If it is known that the majority of citizens want to join the EU only because of the fact that they want a democratic society with the rule of law, a transparent and uncorrupted government, it is understandable why the certain percentage of citizens simultaneously support the government’s intention to develop this service.

EU officials require the Montenegrin authorities to significantly reduce the number of employees in public administrations. The research that has been conducted indicates that the delay in this process, which is generated by social and political reasons, is one of the potential causes why the administration is not more committed to fostering an ICT environment (Radunović, 2015a). In order to have the project “Wireless Montenegro” functioning and to be recognized as a sincere intention of the authorities with the aim of involving citizens in the information society, and to give them the possibility of using electronic communication with the administration, the government obviously needs to change its approach. Thus, if the government succeeds in pleasing its citizens, then the EU requirement will be accomplished as well.

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Figures

Figure 1. The age and number of survey respondents.

Figure 2. The number of respondents: who have used and have known about the service; who do not know about the service; who do not have any device for using "Free Montenegro" service.

Figure 3.a) The number of respondents who have used the service; b) The number of users who were satisfied with the service.

Figure 4. How many times users have been connected to the WiFi network "Free Montenegro"

Figure 5. The number of respondents who have used the service for communications with some of public administration bodies.

Figure 6. The number of respondents who are satisfied with the Government's efforts in improving free WiFi services for citizens.

Figure 7. Those who are among the satisfied respondents with Government's effort on improving free WiFi service "Wireless Montenegro".

Figure 8. The number of respondents who see/do not see any connection between project "Wireless Montenegro" and the EU accession process.

Figure 9. What respondents consider the project is about: for citizens; for satisfying EU officials; something else

Figure 10. A comparative overview of the number of citizens and the number of access points for free WiFi: The cities of Rijeka and Podgorica, and the countries of Croatia and Montenegro.